

Feminist Confrontation and Resistance in Hanan al-Shaykh's Beirut Blues

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Abstract

An epistolary novel, *Beirut Blues* was written by Lebanese writer Hanan al-Shaykh. She was born in the year 1945 in Beirut, Lebanon, to a strict Shia family. Her first novel *Suicide of a Dead Man* was published in 1967. She worked as a journalist in Beirut in television and for a newspaper *Al-Nahar*. Due to the Lebanese Civil War (1975 to 1990), she left for Saudi Arabia in 1976 and lived there until 1982 and moved to London. Some of her novels are *The Story of Zahra* (1980), *Women of Sand and Myrrh* (1989), *Beirut Blues* (1992), *The Occasional Virgin* (2018) and *Only in London* (2000). She wrote her novels in Arabic and it was translated into English. The novel *Beirut Blues* was taken for study. It presented the blues of Lebanese civil war and its effects on the people.

Keywords: Lebanon, epistolary novel, war, grief, destruction

The Encyclopedia Britannica describes war as “a conflict between

political groups involving hostilities of considerable duration and magnitude” (Frankel). It is considered masculine but for a layman, war is often seen as an unpleasant thing. The public is affected by the destruction of war. Their normal life is being disturbed. They either lose their life or loved ones. They live in constant fear. Their home is destroyed. Their livelihood is spoiled. War ruined peace. The Amal Movement was a Lebanese political party associated with Lebanon's Shia community. It gained attention and saw a renewal after Israel's invasion of Lebanon in 1978. It became the largest Shia party in parliament, having sixteen representatives to Hezbollah's thirteen. Hezbollah, Party of God, also transliterated Hizbullah or Hizballah, a Shia Islamist political party and militant group based in Lebanon. Hezbollah emerged in South Lebanon as a rival to the older Amal Movement. It ended in partitioning of Lebanon between Muslims in the south and Christians in the north.

The novel is shown through the sight of a woman. The plot consists of ten long letters written by the protagonist Asmahan to her friend, lover, land, war and so on which would never reach them. The first letter was addressed to her

friend Hayat. She began the letter with My Dear Hayat. As there was no power supply, she was holding an energizer flashlight and shone around the room looked at the painting which was gifted by Hayat during one of her visits to Beirut because the woman in the painting resembled her. She felt that the way the woman in the painting sitting alone in the room with only a little light filtering in through the window reminded Hayat about Asmahan.

Asmahan did not want Hayat to be worried because she knew, Hayat wanted to know about events happening and reassure her that she was safe, while Asmahan absorbed with the trivia of love and sex, and presently with the rat, "How can I answer your questions about the state of the country when my chief worry is the rat occupying our kitchen?" (al-Shaykh 3). She knew Hayat was trying to contact her but for a month the telephone had been dead. She was the first one to ring her when the war begun. Asmahan felt like talking to her as if she was not far away. The thoughts and feelings born of violence seemed real. It was as if she was in love with Hayat. The war put an end to normal life. They had lost trust of their fellow beings.

Asmahan remembered that her friend, Fadila admitted her mother in Saint Maroun's Hospital. They were on the way to visit her mother and she was telling the taxi driver how much she liked the Christians and trusted them hoping to engage him in a conversation. She even wanted to share the chocolates with him

but he remained silent and refused to accept it. He might have thought that the chocolates were poisoned. She started talking about the suffering of the people in the west. The driver was irritated by her continuous talk and shouted, "Life's shit there and it's shit here." (15). Fadila was scared to cross from west to the east and was trying to befriend the taxi driver. Upon reaching the hospital safely, she was relaxed. She thanked the driver and offered "a piece of baklava, a chocolate, a cigarette. "At least you've still got patisseries over there," he said" (16). She promised to bring a box of baklava for his family for the people to protect her mother. People started leaving their country. Asmahan felt like saluting Hayat for leaving the country as she understood that the war would never end and people had forgotten the aim of the war.

The second letter was written to Jill Morrel about the increasing of kidnapping. Both Amal and Hizbullah blaming each other, "Hizbullah says Amal are traitors for calling them troublemakers, and Amal says that Hizbullah's turned Al-Dahiya into a no-go area" (31). Asmahan remembered her mother burning the belongings of the father soon after his death. Her mother lived in the world of movie stars. She planned to remarry and left to the States. Even without discussion everybody knew that Asmahan was going to live with her grandmother and her maid, Zemzem.

During the days of war, as kidnappings increased, she felt stranger in her own country. She had to use a map to

locate the name and landmarks of the places. She questioned herself, "Who kidnapped them? Who's kidnapping me? Is this a civil war, an international war, or a capitalist war? (38). She remembered one of Hayat's relatives was held for a few months, blindfolded and released him. So she hoped that Jill's boyfriend would not be harmed.

The *Publisher's Weekly* remarked that,

Asmahan remembers her beautiful, cosmopolitan Beirut and childhood friends, juxtaposing them with the city's grizzled, suspicious present and the occupiers who took the exiles' places. Druze, Shia (including the gunmen of Hizbullah and Amal), Sunni, Christian, Palestinian, Syrian and Iranian personages figure in the story, though Asmahan seems disgusted with all of them.

The next letter was written to her lover Naser, by Asmahan. The scared neighbour came to visit them for some moral support. Zemzem wanted to leave for Egypt or Syria to escape the war. The grandmother did not approve of the idea. As there was a sudden explosion, they all screamed and rushed out. They almost collided with each other and burst out laughing. The grandmother said that Asmahan resembled her mother and had the sense of humour. Days passed and Ali, a relative came to rescue them. He

brought a big tank. Asmahan remembered Naser wanted to leave Beirut five years back in a tank. Naser boarded the ship which Asmahan could not think of.

The fourth letter was written to land stating, "We're setting out for you, but we still haven't reached you" (al-Shaykh94). The land was not normal yet. The trees were cut down and the buildings were ruined. People were accustomed to use dollars and see George Washington on it instead of a Lebanese hundred lira-note. Everywhere the effect of inflation was visible. They were on their way to the village. They took the upper road instead of the lower road as there was a risk of robbers. Her grandfather welcomed them. Asmahan was happy as she was in the village. She saw opium was being cultivated instead of crops. The trees were destroyed.

The fifth letter was written to Billie Holiday. She felt she should stop listening to the music of Billie Holiday as she aroused her emotions. Ruhhiya was a friend of Asmahan though she was much younger to Ruhhiya. She wished that Asmahan would marry Jawad, one of Ruhhiya's younger cousins. When the talk sprung of Asmahan's marriage, Ruhhiya told she must be waiting for Jawad, her cousin which embarrassed her. Asmahan met an artist who painted the martyrs in Hizbullah and Amal.

The sixth letter was written to her grandmother. Asmahan wanted to let her know about a sort of love relationship between the grandfather and Juhayna. Juhayna accepted him though she was

young. She displayed her beauty to make her presence known. The girls no longer liked to work at home, but fancied working with opium, at maternity hospitals as nurses where they were given training, at schools or institutes of Iranian embassy where they receive free notebooks and in all other businesses run by youngsters of Hizbullah. When Asmahan's mother married for the second time, the grandmother must have sensed Asmahan's intelligence and felt that she could not study properly due to the unpleasant atmosphere at home. They moved to Beirut. The grandfather would visit them often.

The seventh letter was written to Jawad. He returned from France to visit Ruhhiya. Asmahan was eager to meet Jawad. Asmahan blamed Ruhhiya for mentioning often and making her feel she wanted him. She said that she was desperate for any man in this drought. Jawad recognised Asmahan which surprised Ruhhiya. Jawad asked, " 'Okay, if that's true, Ruhhiya wants you to marry me' " (200). He inquired about her family and Ruhhiya felt he had supernatural powers as he remembered even the crack on her table and inquired about it. Asmahan questioned herself that if he knew that she was a trained architect. Ruhhiya told her that she asked Jawad to write a story of her own with his brother and he had replied that it had been written and filmed already. Jawad spoke to her grandfather and she felt that he might be writing a book about them and the village. He wanted to go to the artist's

house. But Asmahan had a degree in architecture and designed the buildings went unnoticed. She wanted Jawad to show his affection towards her.

The next letter was written to the war. Asmahan did not begin the letter with dear as she wrote other letters because the war was not dear. People immigrated to other places and those hiding themselves started returning. She started questioning herself,

What am I doing? Is this the life I was meant to live, or is there another path I should take? I blamed you for this instability, for leaving me in a wasteland without the glimpse of the future. You had a part in destroying my ideas about a new kind of architecture which would allow people to live in harmony with their minds and bodies. When I saw ruined buildings hastily reconstructed with wooden siding and sheets of tin, I heard you laughing at my ludicrous ideas. (231)

Asmahan wrote the next letter to the land Beirut. On seeing the distorted images Jawad closed his eyes. Asmahan remembered her visit to the commercial district after a gap of several years. She woke up from Simon's apartment where he kissed her and asked to wait for him at the hotel in the afternoon. He was a press

photographer. He could not sleep. He wanted sex. He wanted to forget violence. He gave her strength. He wanted always to leave which she knew and he told he would be killed soon as he had seen the several dead bodies piled up in pyramids. The picture was published in the world press without his name. Simon wanted to leave the western sector. Once he was caught at the checkpoint and as he was wearing bulletproof jacket. They were convinced he was a foreign spy and not a press reporter. Asmahan lost her interest visiting the eastern sector though she had the contact numbers and addresses but scared about the return of war.

Jawad was leaving in two days. Asmahan questioned herself, "Why do relationships require physical contact to develop?" (313). Her desire went beyond hugging and kissing. She told Jawad that she loved him. He must be wondering then why did not Asmahan respond to his love. She wanted to ask whether Jawad loved her but she did not.

The last letter was written to Hayat again. He asked Asmahan to go with him. She wanted to die in Beirut. Suddenly she cried as she did not have a visa. Jawad was ready to postpone his trip till she got a visa and comforted her. Upon asking, Asmahan reminded Ruhhiya that Jawad was already living with Catherine and she was not going to live with him. She was leaving the country as others did and might go to live with her mother or Hayat which she had not decided then. Asmahan saw the French visa stamp in the passport.

Asmahan kept her head down in the car to avoid bullets as she read in the newspaper about stray bullets killing people. She had decided to leave the country. The objects around her reminded her of the childhood.

At the airport while they were waiting after the check in, Jawad was scared the plane would not take off and Asmahan was scared that it would. She felt that Naser made her greet the war, Simon showed it to her at close quarters and Jawad was trying to take her away from it. She questioned herself, "What is peace? I carry my war with me wherever I go" (360). She was upset. Jawad asked her reason for being upset, "Do you want me to choose between you? Shall we get married?" (364). She just answered that she could not leave. He asked what happened in those three hours that she decided to stay. With tears she told, "'I love you very much, but I want to stay in Beirut'" (365). He told she might not be like a queen in Beirut and tried to persuade her that each country has its own way of life. He often kissed her as he started missing her already.

Asmahan decided not to stay in Beirut and follow him to Paris, "I'm happy to have made this decision and want to surprise him and I'm the one to take his hand this time and bring it up to my face as if I'm telling him, what I've decided" (369). Without knowing this, Jawad asked her what he could do for her to leave. Asmahan wondered, "how I can let a man like that go" (371). The flight was announced, she left him, "standing

alone in line with his camera and hand luggage” (371). She felt her energy returned, “I went to confront the city which had made its war die of weariness” (371).

Maya Jaggi in a journal named, *The Guardian*, published an article, “Conflicts Unveiled” in which it was said that the novel was dedicated to Najah Taher, who remained in the city during the civil war and with whom al-Shaykh spoke almost every day over phone. Maya Jaggi told, “In Taher’s view, the book was a “cleansing for Hanan, for the guilt of leaving Lebanon. She was also trying to find common ground between east and west, to say we can communicate.”” Najah Taher, a Lebanese artist was a friend of Hanan al-Shaykh. It might be the cause why the writer made the protagonist Asmahan to decide to stay in order to confront the war-torn city.

Michel Foucault’s foremost idea was to take care of the self-first which simultaneously allow taking care of one’s own surroundings. During the war, as a woman, Asmahan worried about the basic needs to be fulfilled at home like food, water, power supply and even worried about the rats in the kitchen. Gradually she moved to worry about the bombs landed in the country and moved to the village to her grandfather. She saw the effects of war even in the village. People left the country and some remained where they were. She mourned not only for the destruction of the country but also for the destruction of buildings. Her mourning for her country did not allow her to board

the plane to France with Jawad. After the dilemma, she took a firm decision to confront her city bidding farewell to Jawad.

The unsent letters in the novel represents the connectivity while “all the other vital modes of communication have been cut as a result of the raging war, Asmahan’s letters...act as a lifeline linking the Lebanese in exile to their friends and families back home and redraw, ...the overall trajectory of the war for Lebanese and foreign readers alike” (Mambrol). Being an architect, she wanted the buildings to protect the people from the destruction caused by the war. She chose to resist and remain in her own country sacrificing her love life hoping to rebuild her life and nation.

References

- Frankel, Joseph. "war". Encyclopedia Britannica, 5 Jan. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/war>.
- Jaggi, Maya. “Conflicts Unveiled.” *The Guardian*, Guardian News and Media, 7 July 2001, www.theguardian.com/books/2001/jul/07/fiction.books.
- Mambrol, Nasrullah. “Analysis of Hanan Al-Shaykh’s Beirut Blues.” *Literary Theory and Criticism*, 9 Oct. 2022, literariness.org/2022/10/09/analysis-of-hanan-al-shaykhs-beirut-blues/.
- Review of *Beirut Blues*, by Hanan Al-Shaykh. *Publishers Weekly*, 5 Jan. 1995,

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